

HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM AND GEOGRAPHICAL ASPECTS OF ITS RESEARCH

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Annotation. This article examines the history of the emergence of tourism activities, development and their impact on the development of countries. Also, the views of foreign scientists on the emergence of the concept of tourism, its types, classification were studied

Keywords: international tourism, agrotourism, tourist, excursion, travel, tourism classification, local tourism, wellness.

Introduction. It is known that the first tourist tourists arose for commercial purposes. In old Egypt, which was 14 thousand years ago, it entered a special hue. The Egyptian Horn Hatshepsut organizes a trip on a sea expedition. In the 6th century BC, the Egyptian pharaoh organized a three-year journey across Africa. And later the Egyptian nobility began to go on a trip to many cities (Greece, Rome). During this period, tourism is organized with the aim of finding wealth.

In order to make a fortune, 2300 years ago Xenophon orders the construction of the port of Greg, the construction of stalls and public houses. This will bring him considerable income. At this time, hotel farm services were formed. Some Greeks and Romans are not far from the city where they live in the mountain, and establish places of rest in the foothills for the purpose of rest, treatment, hunting. Tourism in grew rapidly after great geographical discoveries. K.Liberé describes that in Europe in the 18th century, tourism took on a new look, and tourists travel for the purpose of dating, treatment and recreation, as well as the importance of trade, grew rapidly.¹⁵

One of the first specialists in the field of tourism is Thomas Cook of England. He is a Baptist (priest) who, for the first time in 1843, brings a tourist group between Leicester and City of Lefe, England, to a train journey, gathering for the first time a convict of 570 people, and lays the foundation for the establishment of mass tourism. His success on the tour brings fame to Thomas Cook. It is Cook who develops his work, giving tourists great privileges in determining the cost of tickets (tickets). It provides for the participation of 165 people in an international exhibition in the English city of London by organizing excursions.

Material and Methods. Thomas Cook provides for the first time in 1855 to participate in an international exhibition in Paris, gathering British tourists. In 1851, Thomas Cook and his son form a tourist firm. In 1865, it organizes a trip to Switzerland to relax, gathering wealthy people. Thus, it lays the foundation for the current modern tourism industry. In the 19 century, excursions, trips were one of the most important methods of teaching in schools, higher educational institutions, and became an area that served to collect scientific geographical and local history information. The discovery of the car in the 20 century creates opportunities for humanity to move at a convenient and very fast opportunity. Cars and buses were created to transport people. In 1903, a motorized aircraft was created by the American brothers, and at the same time it appeared in the

¹⁵ Jamoliddin o'g'li, J. M., & Isroiljon o'g, D. R. Z. (2022). DESCRIPTION OF LOCAL HISTORY AND EXCURSION OBJECTS OF FERGANA REGION. 57-bet.

European Sky. Gunpowder floating in the sea also began to be perfected. For its time, liners were built, which became giants. In particular, passenger transport vehicles with a large water capacity and high speed appeared, such as Sirius, Lusitania, Mauritania, Emperor, Titanic. A regular ocean liner "Queen Mary" was built and launched between America and Europe. The progress of sea and air transportation has provided opportunities for the transportation of international sender and its growth. Tourist organizations in the second half of the 19 century in Russia (1885y.) and is also organized in several other countries. One of the common cases in tourism is the busy(booking)of places in transport, in hotels, the stay of hotels, road tickets, schedules and quality road indicators, the provision of sufficient information become a normal situation. These phenomena in many cases were greatly influenced by the aircraft revolution, including radical changes in transport, the emergence of new modern vehicles, the construction of Railways. In 1838, for the first time, the construction of the " Greytvestern " parakeet – screw ship took 68 passengers from America to Europe and poured, thus establishing a regular ship service between the cities of New York and London.

1866 Thomas Cook organizes two groups of British tourists going to the United States. In 1867, the Quaker parachute starts a five-month sea voyage, taking tourists with 60 people on board. During that period, a new area of business tourism soon began to attract a large number of entrepreneurs. T. After the Cook firm, several new tourist organizations began to appear in England. In particular, the Tourist Organization Themes and Sera Lana, the political association of tourists, the cyclist club, etc.. A little later, travel firms and agencies will begin to appear in France, Italy, Switzerland and other countries in Europe. The growth of scientific and technological progress in the development of international tourism, especially the creation of jet aircraft in Air-Transport, has created great opportunities.

The rapid development of the UN to the rise of the role of international tourism paid a lot of attention to this area of international cooperation. The word "tourism" in French is *Tourisme* — "travel, rest", which also means performing sports and universal or political educational tasks. A person who, in 1963, went on a trip from one country to another in accordance with the UN Rome conference on international tourism, stood there in at least 24 hours and used the tourist service is called a "tourist". It was also agreed that at the 1991 conference of the BTT and the UN Statistical Commission on the topic "international tourism and statistics" in Ottawa, the capital of Canada, a tourist will be told to a person who has used the services of historical and other tourist objects for no more than 12 months from the place where he lives without employment.¹⁶ Hence, the so-called tourist or tourist must use the tourist service without being directly busy with Labor. At the moment, a tourist becomes a local tourist in his country, and outside it a foreign one, that is, an international one. When classified according to the organization of tourism, it is divided into two groups: planned organized, acting without a plan. Planned organized tourism is understood as the movement of people regulated by the state on the basis of laws or other regulatory documents. This activity can be carried out by state and non-state tourist organizations, various firms and companies.

¹⁶ Ахмадалиев, Ю. И., Маматисаков, Ж., & Мухитдинов, И. (2022). НЕОБХОДИМОСТЬ СОВМЕСТНОГО ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ И ОХРАНА ПРИРОДНЫХ РЕСУРСОВ ПРИГРАНИЧНЫХ ТЕРРИТОРИЙ. *Scientific Impulse*, 1(3), 732-бет

Results.

Tourism organized without a plan includes the type of movement of people who are voluntarily organized independently. This is mainly done through the organization of volunteer tourist societies, alliances and individuals. The main part of local tourism in Uzbekistan belongs to tourism organized without a plan. There are 2 main sections of tourism, which are internal (local) and external (international) tourism.¹⁷ Local tourism is what a challenge has on the territory of his country (without a visa, customs barrier, etc.) is to travel to the place, relax and engage in other tourist activities. With domestic tourism, international tourism is closely developing, but in domestic tourism, colloquial, transport (given that many travel on their own personal cars) and other problems are much easier. The most important aspect of local tourism for our region (Central Asia), together with the tourist route chosen for the trip, is the religious step, which can be visited by people and relatives, and seeing friends can be done at the same time. By seeing and studying the region in which he lives in local tourism, his spiritual outlook increases, and love awakens in his homeland, and also serves to heal the population, restore working capacity and improve the functioning of labor resources.

International tourism is a trip organized from one state to another. It includes Visa, medical check, currency exchange and many other activities. International tourism can take place in groups or individually, based on the route organized for a specific purpose. In this case, the most important thing is that tourists get acquainted with the historical monuments and cities, culture, art, traditions of this state, as well as enjoy other unique tourist objects. International tourism is also closely related to sports competitions, scientific conferences, conferences, cultural ties, religious ceremonies. International tourism has been developing for a very long time. Because in that period there were no clear boundaries between countries, going from one state to another, from city to city did not cause any difficulties. At the same time, it is known from history that tourism is of great importance in the worldwide spread of trade, culture, art and Science for the strict observance of the rules of the order introduced on the territory of this state. According to the purpose of tourism, it is divided into several types. One of its branches of development today is agrotourism. Agrotourism is a type of Travel organized using natural-cultural and local resources in rural areas.

Discussion.

Improving the living conditions of the population, an increase in weekends, an increase in the material income of the family are the reasons for a comprehensive and effective transfer of travel. This is of course a matter directly related to geography.

Because people want to see the world with their own eyes, and not from the card or the media. Indeed, during the trip, tourists carry out the tourist opportunities of the regions by organizing trips. This is a characteristic feature of Tourism. At this point, it should be taken into account that the types and manifestations of Tourism, organizational foundations, duration, seasonality and age are different. Tourism is a sector of the economy that is unique. This area, like other industries, is an area that contributes its significant contribution to the country's economy, to the increase in its gross domestic product. But it has its own characteristics.

Conclusion.

Firstly, tourism is seasonal in nature and is determined by the occurrence of a short-term movement of people from one place to another or from one country to another. In this case, people

¹⁷ Jahongirmirzo Mamatisakov (2022). IMPROVING STUDENTS' GEOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE BY SCHOOL GEOGRAPHY EDUCATION. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (10), 88-89-bet.

do not move in isolation, but in groups (if done alone-it will consist of a simple trip). This feature of tourism, as noted, is its short duration. In most cases, this occurs for 2-3 days, mainly on weekends. During the holiday period, there may also be one-week, ten-day tourist trips.

Its seasonality is that in most cases, a trip to nature is carried out in the spring, summer and autumn months. Some tourist walks will be aimed at relaxing the winter landscape. In general, spring, summer months are considered to be favorable seasons for travel. According to the international tourist survey, April, May and October are recognized as the most favorable time for organized trips to Uzbekistan, in particular to the Fergana Valley.¹⁸

The second feature is understood to be the departure of tourists from their place of permanent residence to another place. The action of the developer in the goal of making money does not go into this. This movement can be both within one territory, within one country, and inter-country. The place of permanent residence of people is understood as the place of its registration (place of residence of residence) by the relevant authorities. In which place the person is registered, it is usually necessary to live in the same place. It is part of this characteristic of tourism that he goes to another place for purposes such as rest, leisure, study, health recovery (lying down does not include treatment).

Thirdly, the fact that tourism is considered only as a way to relax in his free time, to conduct it actively, is also one of its distinctive features. In many cases, situations such as hiking, tamusha, study in other regions can also occur when people are sent on a business trip. But here it is impossible to introduce it into tourism due to the fact that the goal is to graduate from a particular job. One thing should be emphasized in this is that these activities should take place in people's free time.

Fourth, tourism is not only an economic, but also an important social sphere. Along with the economic efficiency of this, the spiritual, spiritual and intellectual importance is also very great. Thanks to this, the state pays special attention to this area and also establishes certain benefits. People use these benefits only because they are tourists. This also testifies to the specificity and great socio-economic importance of Tourism. Benefits are manifested in the passage of tourist customs posts, payment of taxes, permission for a passport in absentia.

Fifth, tourism as a component of the economy brings income to the host country of tourists, provides solid foreign exchange earnings, increases the level of employment of the population. A hotel will be needed to serve tourists. Here they should be fed. Cash to all, in most cases they provide an increase in foreign exchange earnings if they are foreign tourists.

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